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SHORT-TERM LANE FLOW DISTRIBUTION FORECASTING IN HARD SHOULDER RUNNING FREEWAYS

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ABSTRACT

Hard shoulder running systems are usually employed in order to mitigate traffic congestion in freeways. This research presents an exploratory analysis based on data collected from seven radars across a two-lane freeway equipped with hard shoulder that connects Geneva with Lausanne in Switzerland. The variation of the lane flow distribution ratio, during the days of a week that the policy was operating, shows that, when the hard shoulder is active, it serves approximately 20% of the total users' demand. The comparison of the empirical fundamental diagrams between a normal operating period of the system and another that the system was suspended, indicates a capacity increase and a marginal speed level increase. The cluster analysis, that identified the predominant traffic conditions, led to statistically strong short-term lane flow distribution prediction models of the left lane. These models were estimated for three and nine minutes forecasting horizon, paving the prospective work on optimization of the system in question.

Key Words: Lane Flow Distribution, cluster analysis, short-term prediction, hard shoulder running

INTRODUCTION

Traffic demand increase consists one of the main reasons that triggers recurrent congestion in freeways. Apart from altering the current infrastructure, an ITS approach with less financially and timely expensive requirements has emerged. In the study in question, the impact of a hard shoulder running system in traffic behaviour is explored, aiming to upgrade further the potentially favourable effects to capacity, by introducing as a quantifying parameter the lane flow distribution ratio (LFDR). The LFDR is the ratio of the lane flow distribution per lane over the total flow per direction.

Following the traffic analysis by identifying characteristics of the stream assisted by fundamental relationships of traffic parameters, a cluster analysis is implemented. This unsupervised algorithm derives the prevailing traffic regimes of the study site, namely a two-lane freeway with hard shoulder running system in Lausanne (Switzerland). The classification provides homogeneous groups that in terms of traffic dynamics represent certain regimes. Each cluster is then more accurately fitted by regressions, providing an improved insight of traffic conditions. Furthermore, prediction models are developed that forecast the traffic stream dynamics, in order to respond efficiently to short-term future trends and optimise in due time the reactive managed lane system by activating dynamically the shoulder lane. Inferred by the clusters, generalised linear models for lane flow distribution is resulting to the prediction of the flow distribution per lane. In particular left lane flow distribution prediction models were formed on the hypothesis that the regime of the left lane is determining the regimes of the remaining lanes. The study deduces with the conclusions of the results and the prospect work.

STATE OF RESEARCH

For the premise of this research, the focus was set on managed lanes implementations and their impact on traffic behaviour. Early studies have employed modeling methods for predicting traffic conditions. The models were defined by a variety of parameters and methods, the most important of which that could be acknowledged are presented as follows.

Regarding the modeling methods for traffic forecasting, parametric models were preferred when the subject was firstly arisen, namely historical average algorithms (Stephanedes et al., 1981; Kaysi et al., 1993; Smith and Demetsky, 1997;) and on time-series models, such as the Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) models (Stephanedes et al., 1981; Kaysi, 1993; Jeffrey et al., 1987). Ulteriorly, several models that outperform the ARIMA were emerged, such as state-space models with Kalman filter algorithms (i.e. Stathopoulos & Karlaftis, 2003). Furthermore, data-driven models (Williams, 2001; Ishak & Al-Deek, 2002; Zhang & Rice 2003; Antoniou & Koutsopoulos; 2006) dominated the most recent researches, combined in several approaches with artificial neural network-based models (ANN) (Kwon & Stephanedes, 1994; Innamaa, 2000; Park & Rilett, 1998; Rillet and Park, 2001; Abdulhai et al., 1999; Dia, 2001; Ishak and Alecsandru, 2003; van Lint et al., 2005; Chen et al., 2001), which were proved more accurate in capturing stream dynamics compared to the traditional statistical methods, since the optimal network parameters emerge, and the extreme traffic conditions, the rapid fluctuations and the transitions between states are better identified and predicted (Smith and Demetsky, 1997; Yin et al., 2002; Ishak and Alecsandru, 2003). For real-time and near real-time forecasting implementations especially in highways, these are the key features that are required to be comprised for a representative modeling (Kirby et al., 1997; Smith et al., 2002; van Lint et al., 2005; Jiang and Adeli, 2005). In this framework, wavelets are also enlisted as methods with promising results (Zhang & Benveniste, 1992; Karim & Adeli, 2002). However, based on the objectives of the current study, data-driven approaches are addressing better the subject in terms of traffic pattern recognition (Antoniou & Koutsopoulos, 2006). It is also to be noted that researches on traffic behaviour modeling on near-capacity or congested traffic conditions are better described when are introducing lane-oriented parameters (Daganzo, 2002a; Chung & Cassidy, 2004; Duret et al., 2012) than adopting the kinematic-wave (KW) model (Lighthill & Whitham, 1955; Richards, 1956).

As far as the traffic parameters that could be considered is concerned, flow, occupancy, speed and travel time are used as determinants and predictors in corresponding models, without any discernible indication for the most suitable parameter in terms of prediction accuracy (Levin and Tsao, 1980; Dougherty et al., 1994; Dougherty and Cobbett, 1997; Kirby et al., 1997; Lin et al. 2002). In models for highways' ATM and ATIS (Advance Traveller Information Systems) or Dynamic Traffic Assignment (DTA) systems, travel time or speed is preferred, as the information is more comprehensible for the users (Williams, 2001; Stathopoulos and Karlaftis, 2003; Liu et al., 2008; Vlahogianni et al., 2008; Antoniou and Koutsopoulos; 2006; Antoniou et al., 2007; Antoniou et al., 2011). This research introduces the lane flow distribution relationships as representatives and predictors of traffic conditions (Duret et al., 2012; Samoili et al, 2013) that were also encountered in literature for other implementations in highways. Indeed, (Jaesup and Byungkyu, 2010) concluded that truck volume is a significant determinant of the individual to all lanes ratio, whereas Wu, Amin and Bank (Wu, 2006; Amin and Bank, 2007) concluded that in motorway and freeway, the lane flow distribution relationship between freeway and ramp volumes varies by the time of day.

The prediction horizon, the prediction interval, the area of implementation and the aiming type of the ITS system complete the elements that should be accounted in modeling and predicting traffic behaviour. It is suggested that extreme values in forecasting horizons and data aggregation, along with multiple prediction steps into the future do not result to acceptable accuracy (Florio and Mussone, 1996; Kirby et al. 1997; Smith and Demetsky, 1997; Park and Rilett, 1998; Abdulhai et al., 1999; Sheu, 1999; Ishak and Al-Deek, 2002, Samoili et al, 2013).

In Table 1 the current literature in short-term traffic prediction is presented, according to the approach and the characteristics of each method.

**Table 1: Comparative presentation of traffic prediction methods
(Adapted from: Samoili and Dumont, 2012).**

Methodological Approach	Characteristics	Advantages	Deficiencies
Historical Average eg. (Stephanedes et al., 1981; Kaysi et al., 1993)	- deterministic - parametric - relies on cyclical nature of traffic flow	- simple structure	- impossible to predict dynamic traffic behaviour (incidents, transitions etc.)
Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) eg. (Stephanedes et al., 1981; Kaysi et al., 1993)	- stochastic - parametric - linear or non-linear - periodic predictions	- well-established theoretical background	- not stable & not representative of rapid traffic variations & unexpected peaks - not well-suitable for freeway flow forecasting - difficult multivariate models - weak transferability - need of uninterrupted data series
State-space model/ Kalman filter state estimators eg. (Stathopoulos & Karlaftis, 2003)	- linear and non linear - successive updates of parameters from different time periods during daily observations	- possible multivariate modeling - non stationarity of variables - flexible in structure changes - better accuracy than univariate time series models (e.g. ARIMA)	- demands full state of the system - systems must be controllable - strong background of Hilbert space theory, multivariate statistics etc.
Regression (e.g. Nearest Neighbour, Kernel etc.) eg. (Smith & Demetsky, 1997; Antoniou & Koutsopoulos, 2006)	- deterministic - non-parametric - data-driven - linear and non linear	- dynamic clustering - identifies past or neighbourhood cases of current prediction with similar features - high accuracy (ameliorated via training) & simple structure	- data-driven accuracy - demands extensive dataset - difficult multivariate modeling
Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) eg. (Antoniou et al., 2007; Smith & Demetsky, 1997; Kirby et al., 1997; Kwon & Stephanedes, 1994; Ishak & Alecsandru, 2003)	- non-parametric - data-driven - non-linear	- high accuracy - permits generalisations - suitable for real-time/near- real-time predictions (highways etc.)	- demands extensive dataset - complex internal structure and often heuristic - transferability issues
Wavelet, Fuzzy, Bayesian, Analysis of multi-regimes and transitions (hybrid model) (Vlahogianni et al., 2008)	- Empirical identification of traffic flow regimes and transitions - Transitional conditions detection via flow singularity detection - Flow regime identification - Intra-&Inter-regime Transitions identification	- four-regime consideration & inter-regime & intra-regime - real-time applicable - site-transferable	- not established causality between traffic flow phenomena - identification of traffic flow regimes under incidents and adverse weather conditions not included

DATA AND METHODOLOGY

Case Setup and Data Description

The case study is located in Switzerland, in a two lane per direction freeway between Geneva and Lausanne (A1) with average daily traffic 82,000 veh/h. In 2010, a semi-automatic managed lane system was implemented, with a variable speed limit (VSL) system that succours for maintaining the safety requirements, addressing the issue of recurrent traffic demand increase during peak hours. The auxiliary lane is open to circulation based on speed and density thresholds. According to RGR (RGR, 2011), the definition of the traffic regimes (in six levels) is based on the speed-density fundamental diagrams (Fig. 1b, c) that activate the hard shoulder running and the VSL enforcement. The values of the thresholds are different when are ascending or descending and are finalised after two successive cycles of 9 minutes measurements (aggregated by 3-minutes aggregated data), in order to avoid potential system oscillations of the system when the traffic state is unsettled, based on the following traffic state definition diagrams of the system (Figure 1). Figures 1d and 1e show the thresholds of speed and density for the opening and closing that have been suggested upon the designing of the system. It is also suggested that the hard shoulder should be activated when the threshold for opening is attained, for two successive cycles, even for one section of the site. On the contrary, all sections shall reach the closing value for two successive cycles in order to deactivate the system. Nevertheless, the indicative thresholds are applied only if in agreement with the traffic control center, as the system is not entirely automatic.

Figure 1. Site description and thresholds for emergency lane operation system. (a) Study area scheme. VSL enforcement based on speed-density fundamental diagrams upon activation (b), deactivation (c) of the hard shoulder system. Speed-density thresholds for hard shoulder activation (d) and deactivation (e). (Adapted from RGR 2011)

In the traffic dataset that was used (in courtesy of SMETRA) are included per lane disaggregated data of traffic volume, speed, heavy vehicles percentage and indications of the opening and closure of the shoulder lane. The data are collected for both directions by radar sensors on beams placed every approximately 500 meters. The data were aggregated per $\Delta t = 3$ min intervals, before proceeding to the analysis. The study period is corresponding to one week in December and in March, when the dynamic hard-shoulder system was normally running, and one week in December that the system was suspended.

Methodology

Locally weighted regression

In order to explore the traffic behaviour, locally weighted regression, or hereinafter loess, was employed. Loess was introduced by Cleveland (Cleveland, 1978) as a memory-based non-parametric regression that fits a regression surface to data through a multivariate smoothing. In recent studies it is implied that that loess outperforms nearest-neighbourhood and kernel smoothing and that in dynamic traffic assignment systems (DTA) with traffic dynamics model, speed estimation accuracy is improved (Cleveland & Devlin, 1988; Sun et al., 2003; Antoniou et al., 2006; Toledo et al., 2007). Following the analytical mathematical background of loess in Cleveland and Devlin (Cleveland & Devlin, 1988), the values of the response variable, with y_i measurements, are smoothed as a function of the explanatory, p variables with x_i measurements (for $i = 1, \dots, n$). The response variable is estimated around a “seed” point of a local subset, repeatedly shifting forward to the next point of the original dataset. The predicted data are computed by $y_i = \hat{g}(x_i) + \varepsilon_i$, where $\hat{g}(x_i)$ represents the estimate of the regression surface over a local surface around each value x_i in the p - dimensional space of the independent variables, and ε_i the residual errors. The estimate $\hat{g}(x_i)$ at x_i uses the q number of observations (in range $1 < q \leq n$, for q integer) whose x_i distance is closer to x . According to this distance, a weight in the form of the tricube function is computed (eq. 1):

$$W(u) \equiv \begin{cases} (1 - u^3)^3, & \text{if } 0 \leq u < 1 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where u is the space mean speed. The weight is allocated to each point (y_i, x_i) , so that the weight function is (eq. 2):

$$w_i(x) = W\left(\frac{\rho(x, x_i)}{d(x)}\right) \quad (2)$$

whose range varies from 0 for the q th-nearest x_i to x , increasing as the x_i is closer to x . The $\rho(x, x_i)$ is the distance function running in the space of independent variables and $d(x)$ is the distance of the q th-nearest x_i to x . The fitting and prediction procedure is completed when the objective function, namely the weighted residual sum of squares, is minimised (eq. 4) (Antoniou et al., 2006):

$$\min J(\sum_{i=1}^n w_i \varepsilon_i^2) \quad (3)$$

Statistical assessment of forecasting performance

The prediction models that are presented in this study, are assessed with the following statistical indices (Vaze et al., 2009).

The error magnitude of each predicted variable Y_n^s from the observed Y_n^o , is assessed with the normalized root mean square error (eq. 4) and the root mean square percentage error (eq. 5), for time n and number of observations N :

$$RMSN = \sqrt{\frac{N \sum_{n=1}^N (Y_n^s - Y_n^o)^2}{\sum_{n=1}^N Y_n^o}} \quad (4)$$

$$RMSPE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \left(\frac{Y_n^s - Y_n^o}{Y_n^o}\right)^2} \quad (5)$$

The third index employed for the statistical analysis, is the mean percentage error that uncovers any systematic under- or overestimation in the predicted parameter, namely in this case of the LFDR (eq. 6). It is measured in percentage, so as compare between the magnitude of the deviation and the average measurements (Vaze et al., 2009).

$$MPE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \left(\frac{Y_n^s - Y_n^o}{Y_n^o} \right)^2 \quad (6)$$

Fuzzy data clustering

Aiming to ameliorate the determination of traffic flow conditions and the fitting of the explanatory variable to the responses, a sequence of subspaces will be created, following a clustering technique. The dataset is consisted of total flow, LFDR, speed and density. It will be classified into homogeneous mutually exclusive clusters that correspond to a certain regime. These parameters form a set of vectors $X = \{x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n\}$. A representative set $Z = \{z_1, z_2, z_3, \dots, z_n\}$ of z classes in X is produced by a data clustering technique, where $x, z \in \mathbb{R}^p$, thus the most representative traffic states. Among the most efficient fuzzy algorithms, the Fuzzy c-Mean algorithm (FCM) will be employed for this analysis (Bezdek 1981; Cannon et al. 1986, Adeli & Karim, 2000).

With fuzzy partitioning, one traffic pattern is allowed to belong to more than one cluster with a different membership degree from 0 to 1 with 1 denoting the maximum membership to the cluster, rather than a crisp assignment of one traffic pattern exclusively to one cluster. A number of k clusters are a priori defined with k centroids, which must be placed considering that they represent the traffic states, which will form the initial-seed groups centroids. Each set of parameters is assigned to the nearest centroid, until all objects are associated. To the new classes that have been created, k new centroids are located and each object is re-assigned to a new centroid. The loop is terminated when the location of centroids is fixed. This algorithm aims to minimize the following squared error objective function (eq. 7):

$$J_\beta(z) = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^k A_{ij}^\beta \|x_i - z_j\|^2 \quad (7)$$

subject to:

$$\sum_{j=1}^k A_{ij} = 1, \quad 1 \leq i \leq n \quad (8)$$

$$A_{ij} \geq 0, \quad 1 \leq i \leq n, \quad 1 \leq j \leq k, \quad 2 \geq \beta > 1 \quad (9)$$

where J_β is the objective function for given value of data fuzziness degree β , with 2 indicating the greatest fuzziness in the dataset, A_{ij} the membership degree of vector i in class j , k the number of classes, $\|x_i - z_j\|^2$ is a chosen distance measure between data point x_i and the clusters' centers z_j , and z_j are the clusters' centers that indicate the distance between the n data points from their assigned cluster centers, computed by (eq. 10) (MacQueen, 1967; Adeli and Karim, 2000):

$$z_j^t = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n A_{ij}^\beta x_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n A_{ij}^\beta} \quad (10)$$

The four-step algorithm is starting from setting a number of k points, which represent the initial group of traffic states (objects) and the initial seed group of centroids, in respect to the limit of the membership degree (eq. 8). The cluster center z_j for each class is then computed (eq. 10). Subsequently, each object is assigned to the group that has the nearest centroids. After the assignment of the last object, the positions

of the k centroids are recomputed. The last two steps are repeated until the centroids location remains fixed. The algorithm converges after few iterations.

EXPLORATORY ANALYSIS

Analysis of Operation Impact

In order to assess the impact of the managed lane implementation system on the traffic dynamics of the study site, the behaviour of the network during a period of normal operation of the system (06-10/12/2010) was compared to a period that the system was suspended (13-17/12/2010), studying the evolution of the basic traffic parameters – flow, speed and density - and the fundamental relationships between flow-density and flow-speed.

The evolution of flow, speed and density in time per day during a time frame before, during and after the morning and the evening activation of the hard shoulder running system is presented in figures 2, 3 and 4 respectively. The red line depicts the behaviour of each parameter, adjusted with loess models, when the system was suspended and the black line, when it was normally running. In the latter, the green points represent the parameters as they were observed when the hard shoulder was given to circulation, and the black ones when the hard shoulder is not operating. As expected, during the suspension period the traffic regimes were deteriorated leading to congested conditions, due to the volume increase, combined with the speed decrease and the density raise, in particular during the evening peak hours. Moreover, traffic conditions patterns are differentiated across weekdays.

While the hard shoulder system was not running and for both right and left lanes, for the period 7:30-8:30 a.m. and 17:00-18:30 p.m., the volume increased up to 38% (Fig. 2), the speed decreased approximately 43% (Fig. 3) and the density rose up to ~37% (Fig. 4), mainly during the evening peak hours, as it was computed by the maximum distance between the predicted by loess flows for the two cases. On Wednesday, marginally less dense traffic regimes are observed, presumably due to the scholar scheduled midweek break and the consequential part-time employment of a number of parents and employees in the primary education domain. Therefore, i.e. the 7:30 a.m. peak is less pronounced, as $Q_{max}^N \simeq 2450$ veh/h, $V_{max}^N \simeq 77$ km/h and $k_{max}^N \simeq 27$ veh/km, as opposed to $Q_{max}^S \simeq 2450$ veh/h, $V_{max}^S \simeq 50$ km/h and $k_{max}^S \simeq 33$ veh/km for the suspended period on Monday. In the evening peak hours, the trends are distributed in a wider time zone, maintaining more stable conditions.

It is noted that on Wednesday evening the system did not save the measurements due to a technical error, so a comparison with the normal operation is not rendered possible. Regarding the Friday flow decrease (Fig. 2), the hypothesis that could be formed is that anticipating the commuting purposes of the travelers, in an attempt to avoid a breakdown, the vehicles were deviated to an alternative path.

Figure 2: Flow per hour and per weekday (a-e: Monday-Friday), during normal and suspended operation of the hard shoulder running system, adjusted by loess.

Figure 3: Speed per hour and per weekday (a-e: Monday-Friday), during normal and suspended operation of the hard shoulder running system, adjusted by loess.

Figure 4: Density per hour and per weekday (a-e: Monday-Friday), during normal and suspended operation of the hard shoulder running system, adjusted by loess.

The traffic behaviour variation per weekday was further analysed through the fundamental diagram for flow-density per lane, while the system was under normal and under suspended mode (Fig. 5). As aforementioned, on Wednesday while on normal mode, less dense regimes are prevailing with density that does not exceed the $k_L^N \approx 30$ veh/km/lane in the left lane (depicted by a blue line), the $k_R^N \approx 22$ veh/km/lane and the $k_{HS}^N \approx 14$ veh/km/lane in the right and shoulder lane, depicted by yellow and magenta lines respectively for $Q_L^N \approx 2100$ veh/h/lane, $Q_R^N \approx 1600$ veh/h/lane and $Q_{HS}^N \approx 1100$ veh/h/lane. The left lane remains the main carrier also under suspended mode. For $Q_L^S \approx 2250$ veh/h/lane, congested regimes are observed with $k_L^S \approx 30$ veh/km/lane and dense for $Q_R^S \approx 1750$ veh/h/lane, as the volume is maintained at this level around a cluster of $k_R^S \approx 20$ -25 veh/km/lane. Therefore, the capacity drop is avoided with the activation of the system.

On Thursday and Friday, denser regimes are emerging in all lanes, presumably because of the extended business hours of the retail and leisure sector. On Friday during suspended operation, a capacity drop is noted in both acceleration and middle lane, as the density is increasing up to 45 veh/km/lane, while flow starts to decrease from a density value of ~ 21 veh/km/lane and then stabilizes until maximum density occurrence. A great volume is clustered around values of 1700 veh/h/lane – even if loess failed to be adjusted to the data and the results are acquired according to the dataset – that it is sustained up to 1800 veh/h/lane, where a capacity collapse is conducted, and the flow is reduced to ~ 2500 veh/h/lane for the acceleration and to ~ 1600 veh/h/lane for the middle lane. On normal mode the capacity drop is not expressed, as the flow and the density are increasing up to the threshold that activates the system. Hence, the hard shoulder activation marks an amelioration of $\approx 30\%$ in terms of traffic conditions (density for given flow).

Regarding the lane distribution, the volume is undoubtedly better distributed along the three lanes, mainly in the morning activation of the system. The behaviour of the hard shoulder remains uniform throughout the weekdays. The observations in the emergency lane, while the system is suspended, depicted with black points, correspond to cross-beam measurements at the right lane, due to the non-calibration of the radar sensors.

Figure 5: Density-flow relationship per day. Comparison between system on a) normal and b) suspended mode. (N.B. The observations that appear at the hard shoulder while in suspended mode, are due to cross-beam measurements of the radar sensors at the right lane.)

Flow-density (Fig. 6) and speed density diagrams (Fig. 7) were evoked to quantify the effect of the managed lane system on the freeway, on a Tuesday, day that was selected as representative of the traffic stream, during a normal operation of the system (blue line) and a suspended one (red line) adjusted by loess, in the morning (Fig. 6a, 6b, 7a, 7b) and the evening (Fig. 6c, 6d, 7c, 7d). Idem in these graphs, the measurements when the hard-shoulder is not operating during the day are indicated by black points, and the measurements when the hard-shoulder is running, by green. Aiming to take into consideration the impact of heavy vehicles (%HV), the aggregated speed per 3-minutes of time intervals, was computed as follows (eq. 11):

$$V_{3min}(km/h) = (1 - \%HV) \cdot \overline{V_{PC}} + \%HV \cdot \overline{V_{HV}} \quad (11)$$

where $\overline{V_{PC}}$ and $\overline{V_{HV}}$ are the average speeds for the passenger cars and the heavy vehicles, respectively. In Figures 6a, 6c, 7a and 7c conclusions were drawn based on the three lanes of the freeway, when this is applicable. Figures 6b, 6d, 7b and 7d represent the corresponding relationships only for the right and left lane, excluding the representation of the hard shoulder, even when it was running, for ameliorated scaling comparison purposes.

During the normal operation of the system, the $k^N max$ reaches approximately the 53 veh/km. The maximum distance between the predicted by loess flows during the normal and the suspended case of the system, reveals ~18% increase in the flow the three lanes are comprising in the morning activation (Fig. 6a) and ~12% in the evening activation (Fig. 6b). The actual volume that the left and right lanes are accepting during the morning activation of the system is 17% (Fig. 6b) and 21% during the evening activation (Fig. 6d). The positive impact of the system is laying on the fact that the freeway is serving greater volume at almost free-flow speed levels, namely at 90km/h that is near the imposed speed limit when the system is running ($V^N lim= 100km/h$) (Fig. 7).

Furthermore, the activation of the hard shoulder occurs in the morning at $k_m^N \simeq 27$ veh/km and in the evening at $k_e^N \simeq 30$ veh/km, based on the green points of Fig. 6b, 7b and 6d, 7d respectively, while the designated threshold is $k^D=35veh/km$, implying a potential margin for improvement of the system. However, even with that assigned threshold, the positive impact of the hard shoulder running is translated into less dense traffic conditions for longer time frames.

(a) Flow-density relationship of the direction during morning activation of the system

(b) Flow-density relationship of the 2 regular lanes during morning activation of the system

(c) Flow-density relationship of the direction during evening activation of the system

(d) Flow-density relationship of the 2 regular lanes during evening activation of the system.

— System Running
— System Suspended

Figure 6: Comparison of flow-density relationships with and without regular operation of temporary hard shoulder use system during the morning (a, b) and the evening (c, d) activation of the system.

Figure 7: Comparison of speed-density relationships with and without regular operation of temporary hard shoulder use system during the morning (a, b) and the evening (c, d) activation of the system.

Cluster Analysis

At this step of exploratory data mining, a cluster analysis has been applied, in order to refine the derived conclusions on the traffic regimes from the analysis that preceded. For this purpose the R statistical software was used (R Development Core Team, 2013). Based on observations and sensitivity analysis, for the regular lanes, the measurements of a normal operating day were clustered according to the total flow, LFDR and density, in three groups, while for the hard shoulder, the observations were clustered in two, according to their flow, LFDR and speed. The centroid of the second cluster of observations (depicted with red colour in figures 8a and 8b) of the two regular lanes, reveals that flow is nearly equally distributed. This classification indicates the contribution of the shoulder lane on the decongestion of a particular section of the study area. About 15-20% of the users, proceed to lane changing as indicated in figure 8a and 8c. From the first cluster (blue) in figure 8c, it is conducted either the presence of infringement at the hard shoulder during non-operation hours, or erroneous measurements due to the radars' beam intervention between right and the shoulder lane.

An efficient classification is proposed to be invoked through a rule-based fuzzy data clustering, by which the dominant states will be emerged without losing important characteristics. Even though several methodological techniques have been used in literature, which vary in compact support and smoothness, a hybrid method of wavelet and fuzzy analysis was selected, as the computational effort will be reduced and a more robust model will be established. The emergence of this approach was evoked, following the prior literature review and attempts with several methods.

The procedure always terminates, and regarding its sensitivity to the initial random selection of seed-points as cluster centers, it can be reduced after multiple iterations. The algorithm results to a

classification of the aforementioned objects into groups of one traffic flow regimes each, and consequently to the dominant traffic regimes, reducing also the dimensionality of the dataset.

(a) Left lane

(b) Right lane

(c) *Hard shoulder***Figure 8. Lane flow distribution cluster analysis coloured by cluster.**

SHORT-TERM PREDICTION MODELS

Based on the lane flow distribution analysis that was presented by the authors in a recent study (Samoili et al., 2013), short-term prediction models were developed introducing the left lane flow distribution ratio (LLFDR) as a parameter that could describe impending traffic evolution. Consequently, the conversion of the system from reactive to proactive will be made and an evaluation of the policy before its actual implementation will be conducted. The aim is to provide a short-term overview of the forthcoming traffic dynamics that would permit the more efficient implementation of ATM strategies, namely for the site in question the hard shoulder running and the VSL policy.

In order to be based on representative traffic conditions, and thus predict the imminent regimes more accurately, two time-volume clusters - during peak hours and outside this time frame – were examined and two time-oriented models were developed. For the prediction of the short-term lane flow distribution, generalised linear regression models were employed. The response variable was set to be the LLFDR, based on the rationale that traffic conditions can be described by observing the regime in the acceleration (left) lane. A non-congested left lane implies that the right and/or shoulder lane are in a similar regime. The prediction horizon was appointed to 3-minutes, so as to be short enough to not be influenced by any random rapid fluctuations of the stream, and long enough to predict adequately the forthcoming behaviour. In addition to that, the 3-minutes horizon is commensurate with the data aggregation interval of 3-minutes and 9-minutes.

One of the initial models that were developed was a generalised, covering one day traffic and disregarding the peak hours, predicting the LLFDR 3-minutes and 9-minutes after the current, for a time range from 10:00 to 22:00. The explanatory variables were the current LLFDR, the LLFDR measured 3, 6 and 9-minutes prior the prediction time, the right lane speed, the hard-shoulder speed and a variable that denotes binary the operation of the temporary hard shoulder use (1: activated, 0: deactivated). The function that describes the model is the following (eq. 11):

$$Y = \beta_{R_c} X_{R_c} + \beta_{V_2} X_{V_2} + (\beta_{V_3} X_{V_3} * \beta_{V_3} X_{HS}) \quad (11)$$

where, X_{R_c} is the current LLFDR, X_{V_2} is the current speed in the right lane, X_{V_3} is the current speed of the hard shoulder, X_{HS} is a signalisation of the hard shoulder operation (1: activated, 0: deactivated) and β are the coefficients of the variables. The results are presented in Table 2a (Samoili et al., 2013).

For this generalised model, with n=5880 observations, the predicted LLFDR is positively affected by the current LLFDR and hard shoulder speed, but inversely related to the right lane. This is implying that

when there are high speed levels in the right lane, vehicles circulate in non-congested regimes and thus, lanes changes to the left lane are not imposed, indicating a decrease in the left lane volume and so of the predicted LLFDR.

An ameliorated approach was then developed, based on two time-related subsets. The LLFDRs are predicted from one model for free flow and dense regimes (10:00 to 16:00), and from another for evening peak hours (16:40 to 18:45), while the managed lane system is activated. In these models, described in eq. 12 and 13, the response variables are the LLFDRs for 3- and 9-minutes, and the independent variables are the current LLFDR, the LLFDR of 3, 6 and 9-minutes prior to the current:

$$Y = \beta_{R_c} X_{R_c} + \beta_{R_{c-6}} X_{R_{c-6}} + \beta_{R_{c-9}} X_{R_{c-9}} + \beta_{V_2} X_{V_2} \quad (12)$$

$$Y = \beta_{R_c} X_{R_c} + \beta_{R_{c-3}} X_{R_{c-3}} + \beta_{V_2} X_{V_2} \quad (13)$$

where, X_{R_c} is the current LLFDR, $X_{R_{c-3}}$, $X_{R_{c-6}}$, $X_{R_{c-9}}$ are respectively the LLFDRs 3-, 6-, 9-minutes prior to the current, X_{V_2} is the current speed in the right lane and β are the coefficients of the variables. The results are presented in Table 2b (Samoili et al., 2013).

For the non-rush hour model, with n=1459 observations, and the rush-hour, with n=966 observations, the predicted LLFDR of 3-minutes ahead is positively affected by the current LLFDR, the ratios of 6-minutes and 9-minutes prior to the current, and inversely related to the current speed. The predicted LLFDR of 9-minutes ahead is positively affected by the current LLFDR, the ratio of 3-minutes prior, and inversely related to the current speed.

The models were validated by employing the statistical indices that were aforementioned. As expected, based on the RMSN and RMSPE values, the predictions are marginally less accurate for longer prediction horizons. This could be explained by the rapid fluctuations of the traffic parameters that were comprised in the models, which could not be described. Notwithstanding, time-related models provided more precise forecasts. Regarding the estimation of the predictions, the low levels of MPE (1% to 3%) suggest a marginal overestimation of the predicted values.

Table 1. Short-term left lane flow distribution (LLFDR) prediction models' results and statistical assessment. The * indicate the statistical significance of the variables at the 99.9% confidence level, based on t-test ($p < 0.001$). (Samoili et al., 2013)**

(a)

Variables	10:00-22:00			
	<i>glm_{all3}</i>		<i>glm_{all9}</i>	
Lag (min)	3 (n=5880)		9 (n=5880)	
Intercept	0.47	***	0.42	***
β_{R_c}	0.67	***	0.64	***
β_{V_2}	-0.003	***	-0.003	***
β_{V_3}	0.0002	***	0.0002	***
$\beta_{HS} * \text{Open}$	-0.19	***	-0.17	***
$\beta_{V_3} : \beta_{HS} * \text{Open}$	0.002	***	0.001	***
R²	0.74		0.70	
AIC	-15329		-14423	
Residual St. Error	0.07		0.07	
Validation tests				
RMSN	0.14		0.16	
RMSPE	0.16		0.17	
MPE	0.01		0.03	

(b)

Variables	10:00 – 16:00				16:40 – 18:45			
	<i>glm_{norm}</i>		<i>glm_{norm}</i>		<i>glm_{rush}</i>		<i>glm_{rush}</i>	
Lag (min)	3 (n=1459)		9 (n=1459)		3 (n=966)		9 (n=966)	
Intercept	0.42	***	0.48	***	0.21	***	0.29	***
β_{R_c}	0.26	***	0.17	***	0.20	***	0.21	***
$\beta_{R_{c-3}}$	-		0.17	***	-		0.22	***
$\beta_{R_{c-6}}$	0.15	***	-		0.21	***	-	
$\beta_{R_{c-9}}$	0.13	***	-		0.18	***	-	
β_{V_2}	-0.002	***	-0.002	***	-	***	-0.0007	***
R²	0.20		0.11		0.33		0.30	
AIC	-4959		-4784		-3283		-3257	
Residual St. Error	0.05		0.06		0.04		0.04	
Validation tests								
	<i>lm_{norm3}</i>		<i>lm_{norm9}</i>		<i>lm_{rush3}</i>		<i>lm_{rush9}</i>	
RMSN	0.12		0.13		0.11		0.11	
RMSPE	0.12		0.13		0.11		0.11	
MPE	0.02		0.03		0.01		0.02	

CONCLUSIONS

The study was aiming to assess the impact of a managed lane system in a Swiss freeway between Geneva and Lausanne, equipped with seven radar sensors (spaced 500m apart), and prepare the optimization of the system's operation with the implementation of short-term prediction models. The performance of the freeway was analysed based on the comparison between the traffic behaviour that the system was normally operating, to a suspended period. The time frame that was selected as the normal period was in respect to the seasonality patterns, in order to avoid lateral effects. One of the findings are derived by the fact that the activation of the hard shoulder occurs in the morning at $k_m^R \approx 27$ veh/km and in the evening at $k_e^R \approx 30$ veh/km, whilst the designated threshold is set at $k^D 35$ veh/km. Therefore, margins of improvement are emerged that should be further explored. For the suspended case, the deterioration of the traffic conditions was pronounced, with great magnitude of densities for decreasing speed values, since the network appears congested. Consequently, for the temporary shoulder lane running, even though only a borderline improvement in terms of speed levels during dense traffic regimes, is illustrated, a significantly longer and less dense traffic stream is attained.

Following the traffic analysis, a classification of the observations has been applied aiming to derive the dominant traffic regimes of the dataset, reducing also its dimensionality. Furthermore, the left lane flow distribution ratio (LLFDR) was introduced as the response variable of the developed prediction models,

based on the observation that non-congested regimes at the left lane suggest that non-congested regimes are prevailing at the remaining lanes. Two models were developed, with and without time-volume subsets (non-rush hour and rush-hour), the statistical assessment of which confirms strong prediction estimation.

To the upcoming perspectives are comprised the development of prediction models per multi-parameter clusters, in order to optimize the managed lane system, and a validation of the developed models in further freeway and highway sites.

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